

THE IMPORTANCE OF INVESTMENTS IN THE MODERNIZATION OF THE UZBEKISTAN INDUSTRY

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Abstract: The article presents scientific proposals and practical recommendations on the economic context of the relationship between innovation and investment processes in the global economy and attracting investment in the modernization of the national industry.

Key words: innovation, investment, innovative investment, industrial modernization.

Introduction

Achieving economic growth on the basis of further activation of investment activity and moving the economic system to the path of innovative development strategically requires a new scientific interpretation of the economic nature of investments and the mechanism of their effective use in the technological renewal of the production sector during the transition of the republic's economy to market relations. World experience shows that any country that has pursued an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. Therefore, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, said: "With investment, new technologies, advanced experiences, and highly qualified specialists will enter various industries and sectors, regions, and entrepreneurship will develop rapidly"[1].

In the current economic situation, at a time when competition in the world markets is intensifying, the issues of improving the network and technological structures of the national economy, continuously updating production technically and technologically, implementing deep structural changes in the economy, and

consistently continuing the modernization and diversification of industries are increasingly important in our economic policy. gaining importance, the issue of in-depth research of structural changes in the implementation of such tasks remains an urgent scientific problem.

Analysis of literature on the topic

In the works of foreign and national authors P.Samuelson[2], S.I.Abramov[3], the investment market, financial provision of investment, the development and evaluation of investment projects, the main sources of investment, investment risks, the investment environment in the country and the region, financial investment management, investment activity by the state Many issues such as regulatory methods, investment and entrepreneurship relationship have been developed scientifically.

Romash M. V., Shevchuk V. I. various interpretations of the economic concept of "investment" in the works of , are the basis for the formation of the main tasks of investments [4]. It is necessary to include the formation of resources for the production stage of reproduction.

In addition, Keynes Dj., Pinningo I.P., Yakovets Yu., B.A. Ryzberg, L.Sh. Lozovsky, E.B. Starodubtseva, B.G. Authors such as Dyakin describe the approaches to the definition of innovation by first defining it as an object and then defining it as a process[5,6,7]. Without denying the great contribution of these researchers in defining the essence of innovation as an economic concept, it is necessary to complement the existing approaches in terms of the direction and characteristics of the impact of innovation on the content of the social product value form.

Thus, investments form the basis of resource provision of innovative activities. Their absence makes the process of creating and introducing innovations impossible. The relationship between investment and innovation can be seen in the fact that investments can be made in economic, scientific,

organizational, environmental, social and other areas. And only an innovative approach will bring significant results and expected results from investments in these areas.

Research methodology

The research was carried out based on the principles of dialectical worldview. In the study of innovation and investment processes, an integrated and systematic approach to economic events and processes was used. Logical analysis, synthesis, generalization, induction and deduction methods were used to draw conclusions from the data.

Analysis and results

Special attention is paid to the work being carried out in order to attract investments for the implementation of projects related to the structural change of the country's economy, modernization of industries, and technical and technological renewal. In 2017 - 2021, in the state program for the implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the "Year of supporting active entrepreneurship and innovative ideas", funds of enterprises in the direction of deepening structural changes, modernizing and diversifying the leading sectors of the national economy, increasing its competitiveness, Network programs providing 649 investment projects with a total value of 40 billion US dollars will be implemented in 2017-2021 at the expense of UzTTJ, credit from commercial banks, foreign investment and loans. As a result, in the next 5 years, the production of industrial products will increase 1.5 times, its share in the gross domestic product will increase from 33.6% to 36%, and the share of the processing network will increase from 80% to 85%. In 2020, 18 interstate official visits were made and agreements were reached on 1,800 projects worth 52 billion US dollars.

The volume of investments in cooperation with the World Bank, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the Islamic and Asian Development Banks, and other international financial institutions amounted to 8.5 billion US dollars. Today, 456 projects worth 23 billion US dollars are being implemented in our country at the expense of foreign investments. In 2021, it is planned to absorb nearly 138 trillion soums of investments from all sources, or 16 percent more than in 2020. In this regard, the amount of direct foreign investments will be increased by almost 1.5 times compared to the current year and will reach 4.2 billion US dollars. As a result, 142 modern enterprises will be launched.

Today, the main factors of the development of the industry are expected to be:

- development of building materials industry;
- increasing the effectiveness of bank loans in the development of industry;
- processing of local raw materials;
- extensive use of privileges and preferences created within the framework of the localization program and the International Industrial Fair and Cooperation Exchange;
- to expand the scope of export of manufactured products, to help export the products of small enterprises.

Table 1

Composition of investments in industrial sectors of Uzbekistan, %

Industrial sectors	Years							
	2010	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total Industry,	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
including:	7,9	16,7	13,6	10,7	10,8	10,3	11,3	12,3

Electric energy	25,9	23,4	31,0	39,10	42,3	48,1	52,9	46,9
Fuel	19,6	17,9	13,0	8,2	9,5	8,0	5,5	5,5
Metallurgy	6,9	4,2	3,0	6,7	5,9	4,6	5,8	4,5
Chemistry and petrochemicals	4,1	11,2	13,6	11,8	8,5	5,6	5,4	5,0
To mechanical engineering and metal processing	3,5	8,3	4,4	5,3	5,6	5,7	4,3	4,4
Building materials	15,2	8,4	10,5	8,6	7,9	6,9	4,4	6,1
Light industry	5,7	5,5	4,9	4,9	4,8	5,8	4,0	4,1
	11,2	4,4	6,0	4,7	4,7	5,0	6,4	8,2

Starting from January 1, the forced sale of a part of the income in foreign currency received from the export of non-food consumer goods of the textile and sewing-knitting industry to the authorized banks was canceled. Until 2020, technological equipment, components and spare parts imported according to the list approved by the Cabinet of Ministers, which are not produced in the republic, spare parts and components for the installed technological equipment of the textile and sewing-knitting network (they are also based on the list) are exempt from customs fees (at the customs excluding clearance fees) are exempted.

Production of textile equipment was established together with a number of foreign partners, including the Swiss Rieter AG. "Uztex Group" and "Osborn Textile" integrated complexes were formed. In partnership with major players of the world textile industry, the activities of the enterprises "Indoramaqoqon" specializing in cotton fiber processing, "LT Textile International" for the production of mixed yarn and gauze have been established.

As a result of the structural changes implemented in the industrial complex, a number of positive changes have been achieved as a result of the state's tax-budget policy, price and monetary policy, as well as the measures being implemented to reform the economy in general. Reform of industrial enterprises,

structural restructuring, further increase of the share of private property in industry, formation of management of branch enterprises on the basis of market principles occupy an important place in industrial development.

Conclusions and suggestions

From the above comments, it can be concluded that despite the crisis and various negative trends in the world economy in recent years, positive results are being achieved thanks to the consistent policy being conducted in Uzbekistan, and serious structural and quality changes are being observed in the sectors of our economy. These factors, first of all, lead to the improvement of the welfare of our people and the strengthening of the position of our country in the world community, and ensure the level of stable growth in the economy.

The process of achieving sustainable development of the economy of Uzbekistan is directly related to innovative activities, the transition to sustainable development is determined by the process of implementing innovations, which requires an active investment policy. For the purposes of ensuring the economic growth of the national economy, in the current conditions of the country's economic development, it is necessary to create a system of additional market incentives for innovative-investment development in a strategic perspective, taking into account the requirements of the supply of natural resources and environmental safety of productions of the republic's commodity-technological specialization. Economic growth is able to provide necessary investment resources for qualitative changes in the national economy and technological modernization of production.

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